

TECHNOLOGIES ENSURING CHILD DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIDACTIC PROCESS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. *In the article is lightened the place and importance of didactic game educational technologies implementation in teaching of nature studies in the primary classes and its methodics in the teaching process.*

Keywords: *teaching method, educational methods, oral speech, teaching process, personality, didactics.*

It should be said that the introduction of pedagogical technologies related to the process of fundamental reform of education in our country is a social necessity. Applying this guidance and information in practice is an extremely important and urgent task for teachers of all educational institutions dealing with educational problems today.

Before analyzing these problems, it is necessary to dwell on the following information, concepts and terms.

It is known that the essence of modern pedagogical technologies is to give knowledge to the student and to fully master it. The main requirement for teaching in educational institutions based on pedagogical technologies is to provide new knowledge based on the student's life experience, previously acquired knowledge and interests.

The effectiveness of using pedagogical technologies in the educational process is shown by its versatility. It depends on the solution of the questions: "How is the student's mental state, his future development (or decline) taken into account?" In this respect, pedagogical technology has the ability to design, diagnose and differentiate the stages of personality development. It depends on the pedagogue's ability to use educational technologies.

The use of modern pedagogic and information technologies in the continuing education system increases the effectiveness of the student's acceptance and assimilation of educational materials.

Therefore, personal computers are becoming an educational tool. This does not mean that the personal computer has taken over all the functions of the teacher, of course. Perhaps the student's work with a personal computer provides an opportunity to effectively organize the educational process.

Today, different methods are used for the improvement and development of each field, as well as different methods are used in the field of education.

Therefore, it is appropriate to use the methods of didactic game technologies in the teaching of natural science classes, because the variety of methods used in natural science classes increases the student's interest in science.

The versatility and complexity of the issue of forming a fully mature, perfect person shows its importance for the theory and practice of modern education. This task cannot be carried out without the skills of pedagogical personnel, their maturity, deep professional knowledge, skills

and qualifications, and special knowledge. In this regard, it is important to improve the professional competence of pedagogues working in educational organizations.

As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov noted: "If we can educate intelligent, intelligent, spiritual young people, we will be able to achieve the goals set before us, prosperity and development will be decided in our country." This makes it necessary to train experts who meet the requirements of the time in the primary education system, along with theoretical knowledge, in accordance with world standards, and to improve their qualifications. At the same time, one of the main conditions for the reform of primary education is to train a generation of professionals with great spiritual qualities, embodying human qualities, and working as mature personnel.

The demand of the current era is to fulfill the tasks of raising primary education students to become morally and intellectually mature, well-rounded people.

In the didactic processes in the organizations of primary grades, in the improvement of person-oriented technologies that ensure the development and social adaptation of the child, the analysis of the State educational programs of the educational organization, increasing their quality, on this basis, the development of knowledge, skills and competence of primary education students, regularly increasing their professional competence, mental, physical, it is necessary to ensure spiritual and aesthetic development [7, 8].

The unique aspect of the didactic game educational technology, unlike traditional education, requires the cooperation of the primary school students to organize educational activities without prohibiting their independence and academic activities [9, 10]. Consciously directing them to their activities is considered to increase students' interest in learning the basics of science through effective organization, not to carry out any activity by command, and to give them the right to freely choose without limiting the possibilities of individual needs and interests.

In conducting such classes, the teacher must first of all work creatively in order for the student to gain full knowledge of science, to be moral, to develop the talent of choosing a profession, and to acquire the good qualities of our people [11].

The teacher should be alert and intelligent towards the student, taking into account his interest and abilities, and should treat him like a coach. Only after that, the didactic game technologies used in the lessons activate the students' cognitive activity, independent work on textbooks and additional literature, development of the culture of speech and communication, consciously guide them to the profession, get the goal right in eliminating the difficulties that arise during the didactic game, analyze various situations, prepares the ground for the correct conclusion [12].

Based on the many years of experience and observations of Methodist teachers, it was noted that didactic games are one of the most convenient and effective ways to make science lessons and extracurricular activities meaningful, among other subjects. It is shown that the use of didactic games in the lesson increases students' interest, skills and abilities aimed at deep acquisition of awareness [13].

Also, in order to increase the efficiency of the educational process, the need to use a number of innovative technologies, including role-playing games, cluster, businessmen's game, etc. in science classes, was also discussed [14].

Didactic game technologies used in lessons to activate students' cognitive activities, textbooks and supplements independent use of literature, development of the culture of speech and

communication, consciously directing them to the profession, getting the goal right in eliminating the difficulties that arose during the didactic game, analyzing various situations and preparing the ground for making the right conclusions [15].

In addition, it is known that in traditional education, many processes, such as educational goals, content, teaching methods, assessment of control results, are implemented without a certain system, that is, they are not designed before their implementation.

In the old school of primary education, which consisted of giving ready-made information to the students and ensuring that the students retain it in their memory, there was no thought of achieving a guaranteed result. In primary education, each issue is deeply approached, and pre-planned information is not only given by the teacher, but attention is paid to students' independent work, exchange of ideas with the teacher in the lesson, and thinking about achieving a guaranteed result, traditional and non-traditional education are compared and their advantages are revealed [16].

The teacher introduces new information based on concepts known to the student and explains it. In this process, students are busy with concentration, listening, hearing, understanding, perception, logical thinking, memorization, and recall activities. In this case, the student's interest, need, interest, ability, talent, talent will be the basis of his success [17].

Many scientists refer to the object of education as the purpose, content, laws, methods and principles of the teaching process.

Improving the education system can be seen as an innovation process of introducing modern pedagogical technologies. We understand "innovation" as an approach that is introduced to improve the activities of students of a certain class and is accepted as a novelty by the subject of this innovation [18].

The successful implementation of modern pedagogical technologies in the pedagogical team and their good results depend on a number of factors. They can be divided into three large groups: the factors of the first group are related to the content, quality and other characteristics of the introduced news. In this case, it is important to study and analyze the excellence of the innovation, its experience and compatibility with national and local conditions [19].

The second group covers the factors related to the approach to the introduction of the innovation: the planning of the introduction of the innovation, the adherence to gradualism. The third group is the socio-psychological factors, which includes the attitude of the pedagogical team to the innovation, leadership style, etc. The introduction of any innovation, including the introduction of modern pedagogical technology, and the necessary effectiveness depends on how the members of the pedagogical team accept the innovation and their attitude towards it.

So, didactic game lessons used in the process of teaching natural science in elementary grades have the following advantages: - students prepare for didactic game lessons with great interest, as a result, the efficiency of acquiring new knowledge is high; - didactic game lessons are important for primary school students to test their strength, knowledge, talent when choosing a profession for the first time, as well as preparing them for life.

Based on this, creating instructional and methodological manuals that improve modern forms and methods of education, taking into account the characteristics of age in teaching natural science in elementary grades; - it is recommended to improve the modern knowledge, scientific-methodical training of elementary school teachers in order to further improve the theoretical

knowledge, practical skills and qualifications of students in institutions of retraining of public education workers and improving their qualifications.

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